

Comprehensive Evaluation of EEG Features for Microsleep Detection: Statistical Validation and Methodological Improvements

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Abstract. Microsleeps, short lapses in attention, are critical to detect in safety-sensitive settings such as driving and healthcare. Electroencephalography (EEG) provides a basis for detection, but the effectiveness of features and models remains uncertain. This study conducts a comprehensive evaluation of multiple EEG feature categories, including time-domain, frequency-domain, bispectrum, nonlinear, time-frequency, and intensity-weighted descriptors. These features are systematically assessed using both classical machine learning methods and neural models (CNN, LSTM) under a unified framework with consistent dataset, preprocessing, and metrics, ensuring fair comparison.

Results show that intensity-weighted and nonlinear features achieve balanced trade-offs between sensitivity and specificity, while time-frequency features provide the highest accuracy but lower sensitivity. Tree-based models (Random Forest, Gradient Boost) and neural networks outperform simpler baselines. Statistical validation with the Friedman test confirmed significant differences across classifiers (Accuracy: $p = 0.0011$, Sensitivity: $p = 0.0117$, Specificity: $p = 0.0017$), and Nemenyi post-hoc analysis verified the superiority of tree-based and neural approaches.

This work contributes by establishing reliable benchmarks for EEG-based microsleep detection, highlighting which features and models are most effective, and providing statistically validated evidence to guide future research.

Keywords: Microsleep Detection · EEG · Feature extraction.

1 Introduction

Microsleep detection is important in safety-critical domains such as transportation and healthcare, where brief lapses in attention can cause serious consequences [1]. Electroencephalography (EEG), with its temporal and spectral detail, provides a practical basis for detecting these events [2].

Two main factors determine detection performance: the choice of features and the modeling approach. Simple time-domain features (e.g., mean, variance) are computationally efficient but often insufficient for distinguishing microsleeps. Frequency-domain measures (e.g., power in theta and alpha bands), nonlinear measures (e.g., entropy), and intensity-weighted spectral descriptors (e.g., IWMF, IWBW) capture more relevant dynamics but increase computational cost.

This study investigates two research questions:

1. Which EEG features most effectively indicate microsleeps?
2. Which models best exploit these features for detection?

Both classical and neural models are evaluated within a unified framework, using the same dataset, preprocessing, features, and metrics. This comparative design reduces bias, clarifies the trade-offs between approaches, and establishes consistent benchmarks for microsleep detection.

The contribution of this work lies in providing a comprehensive evaluation of EEG features for microsleep detection. Unlike previous studies that focus on a narrow set of features or single classifiers, this work systematically examines time-domain, frequency-domain, bispectrum, nonlinear, time-frequency, and intensity-weighted features across a wide range of models, including both classical and neural approaches.

All experiments are conducted under a unified framework using the same dataset, preprocessing steps, and evaluation metrics, ensuring fair comparison. To further strengthen the analysis, statistical validation with the Friedman test and Nemenyi post-hoc analysis is applied, confirming significant performance differences among classifiers. This approach establishes reliable benchmarks for feature effectiveness and model suitability in microsleep detection. The remainder of this paper reviews related work (Section 2), describes the methodology (Section 3), presents results (Section 4), and concludes with key findings (Section 5).

2 Related Work

Microsleep episodes, defined as brief involuntary lapses into sleep lasting at least 0.5 seconds [7], are a significant concern in situations demanding sustained vigilance such as driving or clinical monitoring. They occur without the awareness of the individual and can have immediate safety implications. For this reason, researchers have investigated a range of sensing modalities and analytical methods for detecting and predicting microsleeps, with electroencephalography (EEG) playing a central role due to its ability to directly capture neural activity.

Single-channel EEG systems have been examined as practical solutions for real-time applications. For example, [18] demonstrated that deep neural networks trained on single-channel EEG recordings can detect microsleeps effectively, highlighting their potential for use in driver-assistance systems. While single-channel devices are relatively inexpensive and easier to implement, their limited spatial coverage may overlook relevant neural dynamics. Multi-channel EEG systems, in contrast, capture richer spatial and spectral information and have been shown to improve detection performance [56]. However, their complexity, cost, and intrusiveness limit widespread deployment. Beyond EEG, alternative modalities have also been explored. Speech-based detection has been investigated using high-dimensional feature sets combining spectral and statistical descriptors [24], though such approaches face challenges of generalizability in natural settings. Other studies have integrated facial image processing with steering wheel pressure sensors to develop multimodal systems for preventing accidents [25], while video-based eye movement monitoring using the EAR algorithm has been proposed as a non-intrusive method for identifying lapses during driving [26].

Feature extraction is a critical component of microsleep detection systems, and a wide variety of methods have been proposed [37]. Conventional spectral features, such as band power in theta and alpha ranges, are commonly employed due to their established relevance to drowsiness. More advanced nonlinear features, including entropy measures, joint entropy, and mutual information, have been shown to capture complexity and inter-channel relationships with high predictive accuracy. For instance, [56] reported strong performance (AUCROC = 0.93) using joint entropy and mutual information, although the class imbalance in microsleep versus responsive states was noted as a limitation for broader applicability. Spatio-temporal features have also been investigated, with [29] demonstrating improved predictive power compared to traditional log-power spectral features, though performance decreased as prediction horizons were extended [38]. Additional contributions include blind source extraction methods that isolate microsleep-related signals from EEG and electrooculogram (EOG) recordings in simulated driving tasks [27].

Since large feature spaces can increase computational burden and risk of overfitting, feature reduction and selection techniques have been widely studied. Approaches such as principal component analysis (PCA), probabilistic PCA, and various nonlinear dimensionality reduction methods have been tested for their ability to maintain discriminative information while simplifying classification [22]. Similarly, feature selection combined with multimodal integration has been applied to manage data imbalance and improve generalizability [21].

In terms of classification methods, a wide spectrum has been explored, from traditional machine learning algorithms to modern deep learning architectures. Early studies often relied on support vector machines (SVM) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA), which remain useful for their interpretability and efficiency. More recent work has focused on neural models capable of learning complex temporal and spectral dependencies. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been applied to labeled EEG segments to identify microsleep events [44], while recurrent neural networks, particularly long short-term memory (LSTM) models, have been used to capture temporal dynamics in EEG recordings and predict behavioral outcomes [32]. These approaches illustrate the gradual shift from handcrafted feature-based models to end-to-end deep learning systems, though challenges remain in achieving robustness across subjects, balancing computational demands, and validating methods in real-world conditions.

Overall, the literature shows substantial progress in microsleep detection through EEG and other modalities. Key trends include the move toward multimodal sensing, the use of advanced nonlinear and spatio-temporal features, and the adoption of deep learning classifiers. Nonetheless, issues such as data imbalance, generalizability, and trade-offs between accuracy and computational efficiency remain open areas for further investigation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset

This study uses the publicly available Maintenance of Wakefulness Test (MWT) dataset [50], which contains EEG and electrooculography (EOG) recordings from 76 participants (50 males; mean age: 45.6 ± 14.2 years). Each participant completed four sessions per day, two before lunch and two after lunch with at least a two-hour interval between trials. During each session, participants were seated in a dimly lit, quiet room without external stimuli or engagement tasks, and were instructed to remain awake. This controlled setup is designed to elicit natural fluctuations in vigilance and microsleep tendencies.

The dataset provides three behavioural labels: *awake*, *drowsy*, and *microsleep*, assigned according to standard MWT scoring criteria. Because the aim of this study is the automatic identification of microsleep episodes, the problem was reformulated as a **binary classification task**, where microsleep segments constitute the positive class and awake+drowsy segments form the negative class. This is consistent with prior microsleep detection studies where the primary goal is reliable identification of microsleep events.

Following segmentation, the dataset exhibited class imbalance, with microsleep episodes forming a small proportion of all labelled segments. To preserve the natural distribution, a **subject-exclusive stratified** train-test split was adopted, ensuring that no participant contributed data to both sets while maintaining class proportions across partitions. No oversampling or synthetic augmentation was applied, as such operations may distort the temporal and spectral structures characteristic of microsleep.

3.2 Preprocessing

To prepare the data for analysis, continuous signals were segmented into overlapping windows, with each segment overlapping the previous by 50%. Windows containing mixed labels were excluded to avoid ambiguous training samples. This procedure enhanced the **signal-to-noise ratio** and ensured consistent representation of the classes. The resulting windows were used to extract features across multiple domains.

3.3 Feature Extraction

Six categories of features were extracted to provide a broad description of EEG dynamics. In total, 164 features were computed per segment.

Time-domain features included measures such as mean, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, and mean crossing rate, offering basic statistical descriptions of the signal.

Frequency-domain features were obtained from power spectral density analysis, including absolute and relative band powers, logarithmic power, peak frequency, and low/high frequency ratios.

Time-frequency features were derived using discrete wavelet transforms with a Daubechies 4 wavelet. At each decomposition level, mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values of the coefficients were calculated, providing information about both transient and steady-state behavior.

Bispectrum features were introduced to characterize nonlinear interactions between frequencies. These included normalized bispectrum entropy, log magnitude, diagonal log magnitude, and energy-weighted centers.

Nonlinear dynamics features captured complexity and chaos in the EEG, including Poincaré plot indices (SD1, SD2, and SD1/SD2 ratio) and entropy measures such as Rényi and Tsallis entropy.

Finally, **intensity-weighted features** were designed to represent spectral distribution. The **Intensity-Weighted Mean Frequency (IWMF)** describes the weighted average frequency of the spectrum, while the **Intensity-Weighted Bandwidth (IWBW)** quantifies the variability of the spectral distribution around the IWMF.

Each feature group was evaluated separately through classification experiments to assess its relative contribution to microsleep detection.

Fig. 1: Top 20 Features Ranked by Importance for Random Forest Classifier. The figure illustrates the most significant features contributing to the model’s predictions, based on mean feature importance values calculated across all datasets.

3.4 Data Splitting Strategy

To avoid subject-dependent bias, the dataset was split using a **subject-exclusive strategy**. This ensured that data from the same participant did not appear in both training and testing sets. Stratification was applied so that class proportions were preserved across splits. The training set consisted of 80% of the data, while 20% was reserved for testing. This approach prevents data leakage, improves generalizability, and maintains the inherent imbalance between microsleep and non-microsleep events.

3.5 Modeling Analysis

The analysis compared a range of models to determine which architectures best exploit EEG features for microsleep detection. Both classical and neural methods were examined under the same dataset, preprocessing, and feature extraction pipeline.

Traditional classifiers included **Naïve Bayes**, configured with Gaussian distributions to provide a simple baseline; **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** with a radial basis function kernel, tuned for regularization parameter C and kernel coefficient γ ; **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)** with $k = 5$ neighbors using Euclidean distance; **Random Forest** with 100 decision trees; and **Gradient Boosted Trees (XGBoost)** with 100 estimators and early stopping.

For neural models, a **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)** was implemented to capture spatial patterns. EEG data were arranged into two-dimensional representations with time samples and channels. The network contained convolutional layers with ReLU activations, max-pooling for dimensionality reduction, and a dense layer leading to a softmax classifier.

A **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)** network was employed to capture temporal dependencies in sequential EEG data. The architecture consisted of an input layer, one LSTM layer with 64 hidden units, dropout regularization, and a dense output layer.

Each model was selected to address specific aspects of the data: Naïve Bayes and SVM for simplicity, tree-based methods for handling nonlinear feature interactions, CNN for spatial feature learning, and LSTM for temporal sequence modeling.

3.6 Evaluation Metrics

Performance was assessed using **accuracy**, **sensitivity**, and **specificity**. Accuracy was defined as the ratio of correctly classified samples to the total number of samples. Sensitivity measured the proportion of correctly identified microsleep events, an essential metric in safety applications. Specificity measured the ability to correctly classify non-microsleep events, reducing false alarms.

Feature importance was also examined, particularly for Random Forest models, using Gini importance to assess the relative contribution of each feature. For neural networks, interpretability was limited, but training histories and confusion matrices were analyzed to ensure stable learning.

All models were trained on the training data and tested on unseen data. Predictions were binarized at a threshold of 0.5 where applicable, and confusion matrices were used to derive sensitivity and specificity. Results across models provided a systematic comparison of performance under identical conditions, highlighting strengths and limitations of both classical and neural approaches for microsleep detection.

4 Results and Discussion

The results are presented in three parts: (1) feature-wise performance, (2) model-wise performance across feature sets, and (3) statistical validation of classifier differences. This structure provides a clear progression from evaluating individual feature domains to understanding model behaviour and confirming whether performance differences are statistically significant.

4.1 Feature-wise Performance

We first evaluated the discriminative capability of each feature domain using two representative classifiers: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Random Forest. Consolidated performance metrics for accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity are presented in Tables [1] and [2].

Time–frequency features achieved the highest overall accuracy (94%), demonstrating strong ability to capture transient spectral changes associated with microsleep episodes. However, despite their high accuracy and excellent specificity, these features exhibited comparatively low sensitivity. This imbalance indicates that while the models classified non-microsleep segments reliably, they were less effective at detecting microsleep events, suggesting the need for additional tuning to improve true-positive recognition.

Nonlinear and intensity-weighted features (IWMF, IWBW) provided the most **balanced** performance across metrics. These descriptors capture entropy dynamics, geometric variability, and spectral intensity distributions, which correspond well to physiological changes occurring during microsleep. Frequency-domain features outperformed time-domain features, consistent with the advantage of spectral analysis in representing oscillatory brain activity.

Feature importance analysis from the Random Forest classifier (Fig. [1]) further supports these observations, with entropy-based and intensity-weighted features ranking among the highest contributors, followed by selected PSD-based measures.

4.2 Model-wise Performance Across Feature Types

The second experiment examined how different model families perform when trained on each feature domain. Performance results for all combinations of feature type and classifier are summarised in Tables [3] – [8].

Tree-based ensemble models, particularly Gradient Boost and Random Forest, demonstrated the most stable and robust performance across feature categories. Their ability to model nonlinear interactions and complex feature relationships makes them well suited to the diverse nature of EEG descriptors analysed in this study.

Neural network models (CNN and LSTM) achieved high specificity, especially when trained on time–frequency features. However, the comparatively lower sensitivity indicates that deeper architectures or larger

Table 1: Performance of features using LDA

Feature Type	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Time Domain	56%	69%	42%
Frequency Domain	67%	66%	68%
Bispectrum	57%	58%	56%
Nonlinear	59%	69%	50%
Time-Frequency	94%	42%	100%
IWMF, IWBW	63%	73%	54%

Table 2: Performance of features using Random Forest

Feature Type	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Time Domain	56%	57%	55%
Frequency Domain	69%	68%	70%
Bispectrum	59%	61%	58%
Nonlinear	65%	60%	69%
Time-Frequency	94%	50%	99%
IWMF, IWBW	65%	64%	66%

datasets may be required to fully capture the subtle temporal and spectral signatures associated with microsleep events.

Table 3: Results of different models on Detection performance using Time Domain Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	53%	96%	10%
SVM	56%	82%	30%
KNN	55%	56%	55%
Random Forest	57%	58%	57%
Gradient Boost	59%	62%	55%
CNN	56%	82%	30%
LSTM	55%	30%	80%

Table 4: Results of different models on Detection performance using Frequency Domain Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	53%	98%	9%
SVM	56%	94%	19%
KNN	64%	63%	64%
Random Forest	66%	64%	68%
Gradient Boost	69%	67%	71%
CNN	55%	11%	98%
LSTM	58%	82%	34%

Classical machine learning models (Naïve Bayes, SVM, KNN, LDA) achieved moderate performance overall. Naïve Bayes frequently showed high sensitivity but very low specificity, reflecting its simplifying distributional assumptions. SVM and KNN achieved reasonable balance in some feature conditions but were generally outperformed by tree-based and neural models.

Minor numerical differences across tables arise from variations in feature subsets and the subject-exclusive train-test split, which naturally introduces variability in sample distributions.

Table 5: Results of different models on Detection performance using Bi-Spectrum Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	50%	100%	0%
SVM	50%	100%	0%
KNN	54%	54%	54%
Random Forest	59%	57%	60%
Gradient Boost	59%	60%	58%
CNN	56%	74%	37%
LSTM	58%	62%	53%

Table 6: Results of different models on Detection performance using Non-Linear Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	56%	94%	17%
SVM	63%	71%	55%
KNN	60%	60%	61%
Random Forest	60%	59%	62%
Gradient Boost	64%	60%	68%
CNN	63%	58%	69%
LSTM	64%	64%	64%

Table 7: Results of different models on Detection performance using Time-Frequency Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	0.89	0.33	0.96
SVM	0.90	0.08	1.00
KNN	0.91	0.46	0.97
Random Forest	0.96	0.79	0.98
Gradient Boost	0.96	0.75	0.98
CNN	0.89	0.00	1.00
LSTM	0.89	0.00	1.00

Table 8: Results of different models on Detection performance using IW MF, IWBW Features

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Naive Bayes	56%	94%	17%
SVM	63%	71%	55%
KNN	60%	60%	61%
Random Forest	60%	59%	62%
Gradient Boost	64%	60%	68%
CNN	63%	58%	69%
LSTM	64%	64%	64%

4.3 Statistical Validation

To assess whether the performance differences observed across classifiers were statistically meaningful, we employed the non-parametric Friedman test using accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity as evaluation metrics. This test is appropriate for comparing multiple models over repeated experimental conditions without assuming normality. The results revealed significant differences among classifiers for all three metrics, with $p = 0.0011$ for accuracy, $p = 0.0117$ for sensitivity, and $p = 0.0017$ for specificity. These outcomes indicate that the models do not perform equivalently and that classifier choice plays a critical role in determining detection performance.

Following this analysis, the Nemenyi post-hoc test was conducted to identify which specific classifier pairs differed significantly. This pairwise comparison method highlights where performance gaps are most pronounced, providing additional insight beyond the overall Friedman test. As shown in Fig. [3], several

Fig. 2: Confusion Matrices for Different Classifiers Using Non-Linear Features

classifiers exhibit statistically distinguishable behaviour, reflecting meaningful variation in their ability to capture microsleep-related EEG patterns.

The results collectively demonstrate that tree-based ensemble methods and neural network models consistently outperform simpler classical approaches. Their superior performance across multiple metrics underscores the importance of model selection in microsleep detection research. Furthermore, the statistical evidence reinforces the value of using more expressive learning architectures, such as ensemble and deep learning models, when modelling the complex temporal and spectral dynamics of EEG signals.

Fig. 3: Nemenyi Post-hoc Test Heatmaps showing pairwise comparisons for Accuracy, Sensitivity, and Specificity across classifiers. Lower values indicate significant differences between classifier pairs.

5 Conclusion

This study presented a comprehensive comparative evaluation of six EEG feature domains and seven classifier families under a unified experimental framework for microsleep detection. Nonlinear and intensity-weighted features (IWMF, IWBW) provided the most balanced trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, while time-frequency features achieved the highest accuracy but exhibited reduced sensitivity, indicating the need for further optimisation.

Tree-based ensemble models, particularly Random Forest and Gradient Boost, consistently delivered strong and stable performance across feature domains. Neural network models (CNN, LSTM) demonstrated competitive performance, particularly in specificity, but require architectural refinement or larger datasets to improve sensitivity to microsleep events. Classical models such as Naïve Bayes, SVM, KNN, and LDA showed moderate performance but were generally less capable of capturing the complex nonlinear dynamics of EEG signals.

Statistical validation using the Friedman and Nemenyi tests confirmed significant performance differences across classifiers, with ensemble and neural architectures outperforming simpler classical models.

Overall, the findings establish a reliable benchmark for EEG-based microsleep detection and offer insight into which combinations of features and classifiers are most effective. Future work will explore transformer-based temporal modelling, multimodal integration with behavioural and physiological signals, and cross-dataset generalisation to further enhance robustness and real-world applicability.

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